

How to be Reasonable About the Meaning of ‘Ought’

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Abstract: Consider the following two popular and plausible principles. First principle: facts about what you ought to do are tightly bound up with facts about what there’s reason to do. For example, if you ought to Φ , then there must be more reason for you to Φ than there is for you to not- Φ . Second principle: ought is ‘upwards monotonic’ – if Φ ing entails Ψ ing, then if S ought to Φ is true, so is S ought to Ψ . I argue that these two principles are incompatible. If I’m right, then respecting the connections between reasons and oughts requires giving up monotonicity, and so requires giving up the classical semantics for deontic modals. We need something new. I sketch a non-monotonic meaning for ‘ought’ which builds the ought/reason connections directly into the semantics, while aiming to accommodate the data that made monotonicity look attractive in the first place.

It is now very common in philosophy to think that facts about oughts are tied up with facts about reasons. Suppose you ought to go to France on holiday. Then there must be some good reason for you to do so. It cannot be the case that you ought to do an action unless there’s something to be said in favour of your doing it:

(Good Reason) If S ought to Φ , then there’s good reason for S to Φ .

Perhaps we can say something stronger. If you really ought to visit France, then your reasons to visit France must be stronger than your reasons not to. It cannot be the case that you should visit France if you in fact have more reason to refrain from going:

(More Reason) If S ought to Φ , then there's more reason for S to Φ than to not- Φ .

Stronger still, these days many would want to link ought-claims and reason-claims together with a biconditional. You ought to go to France just in case this response is more strongly favoured by your reasons than any alternative (e.g. going to Germany):

(Most Reason) S ought to Φ iff there's most reason for S to Φ .

Call (Good Reason), (More Reason) and (Most Reason) the *Connection Principles*, for short.¹ The Connection Principles play a central role in a great deal of ethical and metaethical theorising.² Less explored is the question of what implications, if any, these kinds of principles have for natural language semantics – in particular, for theorising about the meaning of 'ought', and related expressions ('should', 'have to', 'must'). This paper aims to make a start on uncovering some of these implications.

In the first part of the paper (§2), I'm going to make a case for the claim that the Connection Principles really do have implications for natural language semantics. I'm going to argue that only a *particular kind* of semantics for 'ought' is compatible with the Connection Principles. More specifically, I'll argue that a semantics for 'ought' is compatible with the Connection Principles only if it's *non-monotonic* – that is, only if it fails to validate the inference from

(1) You ought to visit France.

¹ See, for example, Schroeder (2007, p.130) and Parfit (2011, p.33) for explicit statements of these kinds of connections. Since writing this paper, these sorts of connections have been discussed under the heading of the 'Balancing View' in important and interesting work by Thomas Schmidt (2024, m.s). While I don't directly engage with Schmidt's work here, and our respective focuses are somewhat different, there is some overlap in the conceptual territory. For example, it's a consequence of Schmidt's development of the Balancing View that, for any Φ and Ψ , every non-derivative reason to Φ is a derivative reason to Φ or Ψ . By contrast, the central claim in the background of §2 in this paper is that reasons don't always transmit over this kind of action-entailment. I hope to engage more directly with Schmidt's work in the future.

² One often finds these kinds of connections between oughts and reasons being most emphasised by Reasons Fundamentalists – those who think that facts about reasons are normatively fundamental (Parfit 2011, Schroeder 2021). But you don't need to be a Reasons Fundamentalist to buy into them. The Connection Principles do not entail anything about the metaphysical priority of one kind of normative fact over another.

to

(2) You ought to visit Texas or France.³

The central claim driving my argument is that reasons themselves behave non-monotonically. Your reasons can strongly favour visiting France without strongly favouring everything that's entailed by your visiting. You can have good reason to do the action in (1) without having good reason to do the action in (2).

If I'm right, the result is an important one. For one thing, the classical Kratzerian semantics for 'ought' is monotonic (it validates an inference from *ought p* to *ought q*, when *p* entails *q*). So an immediate upshot of my argument in §2 – if it's sound – is that the classical Kratzerian semantics for 'ought' is incompatible with the Connection Principles. We have to choose between them.

The second half of the paper (§3-§4) turns to developing a new, non-monotonic semantics for 'ought'. Beyond its non-monotonicity, the semantics I develop has a couple of distinctive features. Firstly, and most notably, I'm going to build the Connection Principles right into the semantics itself: on the semantics I develop, if *S ought to Φ* is true, it follows – just as a matter of semantic entailment – that there's more reason for *S* to *Φ* than for *S* to not-*Φ*. Secondly, I'm going to develop a semantics for the weak modals ('ought', 'should') in tandem with a semantics for the strong modals ('have to', 'must'). On the semantics I present, the weak and strong modals not only have different meanings (*S has to Φ* will entail *S ought to Φ*, but not vice versa), they also have different logics. While 'ought' is non-monotonic, my semantics has 'have to' continuing to obey (a limited kind of) monotonicity. I'll argue that this manoeuvre not only enjoys some intuitive support, but it also allows us to capture much of the data that's standardly used to motivate monotonic analyses of 'ought'.

³ In philosophy and deontic logic, the principle in the background here – that when *p* entails *q*, *ought p* entails *ought q* – is standardly called *Inheritance*. The 'monotonic'/'non-monotonic' terminology is more commonly used by natural language semanticists, but has also been used in philosophy (e.g. Muñoz & Spencer 2020).

§1 Preliminaries: monotonicity and the classical picture of ‘ought’

I begin with a definition of monotonicity. Let’s say *linguistic environments* are sentences where phrases have been removed – things like “A __ walked” or “Sally wanted __”. A linguistic environment is *upwards monotonic* just in case you can always replace an expression that fills the blank space “__” with something *weaker*, and preserve truth. For example, “Justin drank __” is upwards monotonic: if “Justin drank wine” is true, then “Justin drank liquid” is true too. An environment is *downwards monotonic* just in case you can always replace the expression that fills the “__” with something *stronger* and preserve truth. For example, “Justin didn’t drink __” is downwards monotonic: if “Justin didn’t drink liquid” is true, then “Justin didn’t drink wine” is true too. An environment is *non-monotonic* if it’s neither upwards monotonic nor downwards monotonic.

What is it, precisely, for one expression to be stronger or weaker than another? When we’re dealing with propositions, the relevant notion of strength is entirely familiar: p is stronger than q iff p entails q . For expressions that don’t denote propositions, we’ll need to look to one of the more expansive notions of entailment that linguists have offered.⁴ But thankfully we don’t need to get too far into the weeds of these issues here. This paper focuses on action descriptions, and in this domain the relevant notion of strength/weakness is intuitive and familiar: Φ ing is stronger than Ψ ing iff it’s impossible for an agent to Φ without thereby Ψ ing. For example, the action-description ‘...eat a red apple’ is stronger (more specific) than ‘...eat an apple’, but weaker (less specific) than ‘...eat a dark red apple’.

‘Ought’ is certainly not downwards monotonic. (It doesn’t follow the claim that S ought to eat an apple that S ought to eat a red apple.) Is it upwards monotonic? According to the classical, Kratzerian semantics for ‘ought’, the answer is *yes*. Given some function f which maps contexts to sets of worlds that are ideal according to the standards of that context, we can state the basic idea behind the classical semantics as follows:

⁴ For example, Blumberg & Hawthorne (2021) suggest appealing to the generalised notion of entailment given in Schlenker (2009, 14).

Classical Semantics (simple version): *S ought to Φ* is true in context *c* iff all worlds in $f(c)$ are worlds where $S \Phi$ s.⁵

Suppose *S ought to Φ* is true in some context *c*, and that Φ ing entails Ψ ing. On the classical semantics it follows, trivially, that *S ought to Ψ* is true in that same context. (For notice that if all the worlds in $f(c)$ are Φ -worlds, and every Φ -world is a Ψ -world, then every world in $f(c)$ must be a Ψ -world.) And in many cases this seems like the right result. Surely, if I ought to drive under 30mph then I ought to drive under 40mph. If I ought to paint my house pink, then I ought not paint it black.

Nonetheless, the fact that the classical semantics makes ‘ought’ upwards monotonic has been controversial, especially in the philosophical literature. For there are well-known paradoxes which put pressure on this kind of inference. Firstly, there’s Ross’s Paradox (Ross, 1941). You ought to mail this letter to your friend. *Mailing the letter* entails *mailing it or burning it*. But it seems wrong to say that you ought to mail the letter or burn it. Secondly, there’s Jackson & Pargetter’s (1986) famous *Professor Procrastinate*:

Professor Procrastinate: Procrastinate is invited to review a book. It would be best if he accepted the invitation and wrote the review. It would be worst if he accepted the invitation and didn’t write the review. It is not so bad if he rejects the invitation, for then the editor can just find someone else. As it happens, if Procrastinate accepts the review, he won’t write it. (He’ll just procrastinate instead.)

If Procrastinate accepts the invitation, things will go horribly wrong. So, it seems this is false:

(3) Procrastinate ought to accept the invitation.

On the other hand, it’s best if he writes the review. So, this looks true:

⁵ See Kratzer (1991). Kratzer’s own semantics is more sophisticated, distinguishing between two contextually-determined variables (a modal base and an ordering source).

- (4) Procrastinate ought to accept the invitation and write the review.

But that's just a violation of upwards monotonicity, as *accepting and writing* entails *accepting*.

However, defenders of the classical semantics have tended to find ways of blunting the force of these kinds of counterexamples. The popular response to Ross's Paradox is to leverage resources from pragmatics, and insist that "You ought to mail the letter or burn it" isn't false, just misleading.⁶ The classic response to Professor Procrastinate is to insist that the context shifts between evaluating (3) and (4): when we judge the former false we're supposing it's impossible that Procrastinate write the review; when we judge the latter true we're smuggling in worlds where Procrastinate fulfils his obligations.⁷

The current debate, as I see it, is at an impasse. The next part of this paper can be seen as presenting a new argument against monotonicity. I'm going to argue that reason ascriptions (e.g. "there is good reason to ___") are non-monotonic, and therefore that only a semantics for 'ought' which rejects monotonicity will be able to capture the Connection Principles.

§2 A case for reason non-monotonicity

2.1 Suzy's game

The Connection Principles link ought-claims together with linguistic environments of this form:

There is good reason for S to ___

There's more reason for S to ___ than for S not to ___

There's most reason for S to ___

⁶ For an example of one among many who take this route, see Wedgwood (2006).

⁷ For this kind of diagnosis of Professor Procrastinate, see von Fintel (2012).

These environments are clearly not downwards monotonic. (I can have good reason to drink wine without having good reason to drink a barrelful of wine.) The less obvious claim I want to defend is that these reason ascriptions are not upwards monotonic either: sometimes Φ ing entails Ψ ing, there's good reason to Φ , but there's not good reason to Ψ . Mutatis mutandis for 'more reason' and 'most reason'.⁸

Take a look at the following case:

Suzy's game: Suzy's bills are starting to pile up. Luckily for Suzy, she's about to be given the opportunity to earn some money. Suzy is led into a room with a table. On top of the table there's a game, which consists of a panel with buttons labelled 1-100. In order to play the game, she simply needs to press one of the buttons. If Suzy presses the winning button, £100 will be deposited into her bank account. If she presses any other button, £1000 will be extracted from her bank account. Also on the table is £90 in cash. Suzy can either play the game (by pushing one of the buttons) or she can take the cash, but she can't do both. Suzy knows all this, but she doesn't know the location of the winning button. As it happens, the winning button is Button 3.

Consider the following sentences (labelled 'RG' for 'reason to play the game'):

(RG_i) There's good reason for Suzy to play the game.

(RG_{ii}) There's more reason for Suzy to play the game than for her not to play.

(RG_{iii}) There's most reason for Suzy to play the game.

I take it these sentences are naturally judged to be false in the case described. And this initial judgement is only reinforced once we turn our attention to the weights of the various normatively relevant considerations in the case. It's easy to think of reasons *against* Suzy's playing the game. Suzy plays the game iff she pushes Button 1 or Button 2... or Button 100. If Suzy does *that*, she's likely to lose £1000. That's clearly a strong

⁸ This puts me in opposition to accounts of reasons given in Portmore (2019) and Schmidt (2024, m.s.).

reason for her not to do it. On the flipside, it's hard to identify any weighty reasons for her to play. If she plays the game, she *might* win £100. But in general, the mere fact that [if you Φ something good might happen] is not a weighty reason to Φ . So she has a strong reason against playing and only a weak reason to play. It seems that the sentences in (RG) are false.

Now consider:

(R3_i) There's good reason for Suzy to push Button 3.

(R3_{ii}) There's more reason for Suzy to push Button 3 than there is for her not to.

(R3_{iii}) There's most reason for Suzy to push Button 3.

I take it that now our judgements are different. For there do seem to be weighty reasons for Suzy to push Button 3. Here's one: she needs money! It is bad for Suzy to need money, and pushing Button 3 would get her money; so the fact she needs money is a reason for her to push Button 3. What's more, there are no equally weighty reasons counting against pushing Button 3 – it's not as though pushing Button 3 comes with any downsides or costs. So there's a strong reason for her to do it, and no reason for her not to do it. Taking all relevant considerations into account, it seems that there's more reason for her to push Button 3 than to do anything else. So, it seems, each of the (R3) sentences has a true reading.

Now let me be clear: I am not denying that the (R3) sentences *also* have false readings. I take it that there's a sense of 'reason' – a 'subjective' sense – on which it's true to say that Suzy has *no good reason at all* to push Button 3.⁹ (This is the sense of 'reason' we use when assessing an agent's rationality, their

⁹ According to one view, your subjective reasons are just objective reasons that you possess ('have'). See Lord (2018). On another view, there are just two distinct reason relations here – a subjective one and an objective one. See Schroder (2008). Other views posit yet more fine-grained distinctions. See Fogal & Worsnip (2021).

blameworthiness, etc.) My claim isn't that the (R3) sentences don't have false readings; my claim is that, in contrast with the sentences in (RG), they also have true ones.¹⁰

But now we have an apparent monotonicity violation. Suzy *plays the game* by pushing Button 1, or Button 2... or Button 100. So *pushing Button 3* entails *playing the game*.¹¹ If I'm right the (R3) sentences have a true reading but the (RG) sentences don't, then the sentences in (R3) do not entail their counterparts in (RG). It follows that the reason-ascriptions in question are not upwards monotonic.

That we see this kind of monotonicity-violation in *Suzy's Game* is not surprising, I think, once we attend to how reasons can fail to transmit over action-entailment even in rather ordinary cases.¹² Suppose I promise Billy I'll drive him to Disney World. But then, rather than driving Billy, I start driving Billy's little sister instead (leaving Billy at home crying in his room). On the hypothesis that reasons always transmit over action-entailment, I'm doing something – namely, *driving a child to Disney World* – which the promise I made to Billy counted in favour of. But this seems like the wrong way of describing what's going on. The

¹⁰ Some philosophers will likely insist that *there is no sense* of the word 'reason' on which there's reason for Suzy to push Button 3 in the case described. (See, e.g., remarks in Kiesewetter, 2018b, 96-7). I disagree, but I also don't want to litigate this issue here. As it happens, I suspect we can generate the kind of judgements I'm after even if the agent concerned is fully informed. Those who insist that the (R3) sentences are false in *Suzy's Game* can feel free to use the following alternate case throughout the paper.

Suzy's Game Without Ignorance. Once again Suzy is choosing between pushing a button and taking the cash. And once again, Button 3 remains her best option with the £90 cash in a close second place. This time, Suzy knows that Button 3 is the winning button. But Suzy is deeply superstitious: she sees 3 as a tremendously unlucky number, so she would strongly prefer not to push it. Pushing Button 3 is still an option for Suzy (if she decided to push Button 3, she would do so) but if she plays the game she's very likely to push a different button.

¹¹ I sometimes hear the worry that the action-description 'play the game' has the connotation that some kind of random choice is taking place, and hence that *pushing Button 3* doesn't entail *playing the game*. That is not the reading of 'play the game' I intend. Regardless, this issue can be circumvented just by tweaking the case. (For example, rather than pushing buttons, we could say that Suzy has to choose between a hundred different liquids. She wins the game iff she drinks Liquid 3. Then the action description 'play the game' can be replaced with 'drink liquid', which clearly has no connotation of random picking.)

¹² I'm not claiming here that reasons *always* fail to transmit over action-entailment. For example, in most typical cases, your reasons to drive under 30mph (e.g. *that you're in a small village*) are going to be equally strong reasons to drive under 40mph. So, in most typical cases you'll have at least as much reason to drive under 40mph as you do to drive under 30mph. (As you can probably guess, I think it's for this reason that we're quick to make the inference from *you ought to drive under 30mph* to *you ought to drive under 40mph*.)

promise counted in favour of taking Billy *specifically*. It does not offer normative support for just taking some child or other.¹³

The same goes in the case of Suzy. Take the fact that Suzy needs money. This fact is a reason for Suzy to push Button 3 specifically. It's not a reason for her to just push some button or other between 1 and 100. After all, it counts in favour of pushing Button 3 *because*, if Suzy pushes Button 3, she'll get money. And it's simply not true that if Suzy plays the game she'll get money. On the contrary, if Suzy plays the game she'll likely lose a lot. (So, if anything, we'd expect the fact that Suzy needs money to be a reason *against* her playing the game, not a reason for her to do so.)

Suzy's Game has a similar structure to some of the alleged counterexamples to the monotonicity of 'ought'.¹⁴ So you might reasonably wonder whether the same strategies that have been used to defend the monotonicity of 'ought' against Ross's Paradox or *Professor Procrastinate* could be replicated here to defend the monotonicity of 'reason'. I turn to this question now.

2.2 Pragmatic responses

Here's a classic response to Ross's Paradox. The claim that you ought to mail the letter does indeed entail the following:

- (5) You ought to mail the letter or burn it.

¹³ The above remarks do not necessarily put me in opposition to those who think that reasons transmit from ends to necessary *means* (c.f. Kiesewetter 2015). Taking a child to Disney World isn't a *means* of taking Billy. Pushing some button between 1 and 100 isn't a *means* of pushing Button 3. But the remarks do put me in opposition to interesting recent work by Thomas Schmidt (2024, m.s.), who endorses the thesis that reasons transmit over action-entailment. Schmidt (m.s.) appeals to pragmatics to blunt the force of intuitions to the contrary. See below for my worries with this kind of strategy. For Schmidt (2024), the thesis follows from the claims that: (i) reasons to Φ are reasons against every not- Φ entailing option; (ii) reasons against an action are reasons not to do it. If p is a reason to Φ , it follows from (i) that p is a reason against $\sim(\Phi$ or $\Psi)$. And so, from (ii), it follows that p is a reason to Φ or Ψ . For an argument against (i) see Arridge (2025), for an argument against (ii) see Snedegar (2018).

¹⁴ In particular, it's structurally similar to *Professor Procrastinate*, just tweaked to remove certain confounds.

Of course, (5) sounds objectionable. But that's consistent with its being true. The reason why (5) sounds objectionable, this response says, is that it implicates (but does not entail) the following false sentence:

(6) You can burn the letter.

Precisely how this implicature is supposed to be generated is controversial. But the most basic story would go something like this. There's a stronger alternative to (5) – namely, *you ought to mail the letter* – which the speaker chose not to assert. The fact that the speaker chose not to assert this, despite its being a stronger relevant alternative, suggests that the speaker believes it to be false. But if the speaker thinks *you ought to mail the letter* is false, but (5) is true, it follows that the speaker must believe (6). Hence the implicature.

Undeniably, speakers are inclined to infer (6) from (5). And I have no objection to the idea that the best explanation of this 'free choice inference' is going to be broadly pragmatic. I'm also willing to grant (for the sake of argument) that pointing to such an explanation blunts much of the force of Ross's Paradox.¹⁵ What I'm sceptical of is the idea that this kind of response has any application in the present case. That's not to say we don't see similar free choice phenomena with reason-locutions – I suspect we do. Embedding disjunctions under 'there is reason to...' does seem to prompt free choice inferences: it is natural to infer from *there is good reason to Φ or Ψ* to *there is good reason to Φ and good reason to Ψ* . And indeed, I have no objection to the idea that our inclination to make this inference can be given some broadly pragmatic explanation. The trouble, however, is that none of this gets any grip in the present case, given that the sentences we're interested in aren't disjunctive.

Perhaps it's true that an assertion of the explicitly disjunctive sentence (7a) would tend to communicate (7b):

(7a) There is good reason for Suzy to push Button 1 or Button 2 or Button 3 or... (etc.)

¹⁵ See Cariani (2011) for worries with this kind of pragmatic explanation. See von Stechow (2012) for a response to Cariani.

(7b) There is good reason for Suzy to push Button 1.

And perhaps it's true that the best explanation of our inclination to make this inference is going to be some broadly pragmatic one. None of this is relevant to the question at hand, because (7a) is not the sentence we are interested in. The sentence we're interested in is:

(RG_i) There is good reason for Suzy to play the game.

And it simply isn't plausible to claim that (RG_i) implicates (7b).¹⁶ Certainly, it's not normally the case that when Φ ing is a way of Ψ ing, and someone asserts that there's good reason to Ψ , we take them to be saying that there's good reason to Φ . No one would seriously suggest that "there's good reason for Bob to have some wine" has the implicature that there's good reason for Bob to drink nine glasses, or that "there's good reason to watch a movie" has the implicature that there's good reason to watch the worst movie of the year. We shouldn't expect the analogous implicature here either.

2.3 Contextualist responses

A perhaps more promising way of pushing back is to endorse some kind of monotonicity-preserving contextualism about reasons ascriptions. In broad brushstrokes, such an account will say the following. There is no single context in which the sentences in (R3) are true and those in (RG) are false. But the (R3) sentences and the (RG) sentences are most naturally evaluated with respect to different contexts. While the sentences in (R3) are naturally evaluated with respect to a context in which they're true, those in (RG) are most naturally evaluated with respect to a context in which they're false.

¹⁶ Of course, Suzy performs the action in (7a) iff she performs the action in (RG_i). But it doesn't follow from the fact that (7a) implicates (7b), and that (RG_i) and (7a) are (in the context) truth-conditionally equivalent, that (RG_i) implicates (7b). Truth-conditionally equivalent sentences often have different implicatures.

One way of testing the contextualist's hypothesis is to see whether we can conjoin the sentences in (R3) with the negations of the sentences in (RG). I think we can do so. These sound fine to my ears:

- (8a) There isn't good reason for Suzy to play the game, but there is good reason for her to push Button 3.
- (8b) There's more reason for Suzy to take the cash than play the game, but there's more reason for Suzy to push Button 3 than take the cash.
- (8c) There's most reason for Suzy to push Button 3, but there isn't most reason for her to play the game.

Assuming there are no mid-sentence context shifts here, the apparent acceptability of (8a)-(8c) would suggest that monotonicity violations can occur within a single context, contrary to the contextualist strategy.

But the contextualist can bite back. For intuitions here are undeniably fragile, and the data are something of a mixed bag. Consider:

- (9) ? There's good reason for Suzy to push Button 3, but not for her to push a button.

So I'd rather not rely on the conjunction data.¹⁷ Instead, all I'd like to point out here is that the contextualist has an explanatory burden – an explanatory burden which I think they'll find difficult to discharge. It's no use just saying that there are contexts in which the sentences in (R3) are true, and other contexts in which the sentences in (RG) are false. What's needed is an account which *predicts* the context is likely to shift in such a way that we judge the former sentence true and the latter false. Only then do we have an explanation of our judgements.

¹⁷ I do not have an account to offer here as to why (9) is degraded. But it's worth pointing out, following Blumberg & Hawthorne (2022, §4), that we can get (9)-like data going even for environments that are clearly non-monotonic. Consider Blumberg & Hawthorne's example of *fear*. Fear reports are non-monotonic: I can fear that I'll live for exactly three more days without fearing that I'll live for more than two. Yet it sounds very strange to say:

- ? She fears that Michael is going to be disruptive, but she doesn't fear that a boy will be disruptive.

It's easiest to see what I mean by getting an example of a contextualist account on the table. Consider *contrastivism* about reasons – the idea that reason ascriptions are made relative to sets of mutually exclusive alternatives, determined by the context.¹⁸ One might try to leverage a contrastivist picture of reasons to rescue monotonicity. For there are two ways of carving up the options relative to which we might assess (R3) and (RG):

A_{Fine} : {*Push Button 1, Push Button 2, Push Button 3... Take the Cash*}

A_{Coarse} : {*Play the Game, Take the Cash*}

Inspired by Blumberg & Hawthorne's (2021) analysis of 'ought', the contextualist could try to say something like the following:

“ p is a reason for S to X ” is true, relative to a set of alternatives A , iff there's an action Φ in A such that p favours Φ ing more than any other option in A , and Φ ing entails X ing.

Such an account makes reason ascriptions monotonic: in no single context will p is a reason for S to Φ be true and p is a reason for S to Ψ be false, when Φ ing entails Ψ ing. Nonetheless, the contextualist might hope that this kind of account is a good fit for our non-monotonic intuitions: perhaps the reason why we judge the sentences in (R3) to be true and those in (RG) to be false is that we're judging the former relative to A_{Fine} and the latter relative to A_{Coarse} .

This is all well and good, but notice that this isn't really an explanation of our judgements at all. Yes, the sentences in (RG) are false relative to coarse-grained partition, A_{Coarse} . But they're *true* relative to the fine-grained one, A_{Fine} . (The fact *Suzy needs money* favours pushing Button 3 more than any other alternative in A_{Fine} , and pushing Button 3 entails playing the game.) Since there's a salient partition of Suzy's options relative to which the sentences in (RG) come out true, this kind of contextualism would predict that the

¹⁸ For an introduction to reasons contrastivism, see Snedegar (2017).

sentences in (RG) should have a true reading. But they don't seem to. Unless the contextualist can motivate the claim that the context shifts in the way they claim between our evaluation of (R3) and our evaluation of (RG), our initial judgements remain unexplained.¹⁹

Now to be clear, nothing I've said shows that it's impossible to make some kind of broadly contextualist, monotonicity-preserving story work. But until we have such a story on the table, I think we ought to take the appearances at face value. Suzy's reasons strongly support pushing Button 3. They do not strongly support playing the game.

§3 Where next?

If 'ought' is upwards monotonic, it follows from...

- (i) Suzy ought to push Button 3

... that...

- (ii) Suzy ought to play the game.

Given the Connection Principles, it follows from (ii) that

- (RG_i) There's good reason for Suzy to play the game.

¹⁹ Blumberg & Hawthorne (2021) face a similar challenge when it comes to explaining our responses to Professor Procrastinate. Why do we hear "Procrastinate ought to accept" as false, when there's a fine-grained partition of Procrastinate's options – {*accept & write, accept & don't write, don't accept*} – on which it's true? Their response is that speakers have a preference for evaluating ought-claims relative to sets of options that are immediately open to agents – {*accept, don't accept*} – rather than those which include temporally extended actions. But this will not help us here. None of the actions in {*Push Button 1, Push Button 2... Take the cash*} are temporally extended.

But I've just argued (RG_i) has no true reading. Given (i) has a true (objective) reading, and (RG_i) doesn't, we must either reject monotonicity or the Connection principles.

One possible response, at this stage, is just to reject the Connection Principles. This option deserves to be taken seriously. The Connection Principles constitute one way of connecting facts about oughts with facts about reasons, but I haven't given you an argument for thinking that they constitute the only way, or the best way. Indeed, there are philosophers who explicitly reject the Connection Principles, while still aiming to capture the idea that facts about oughts are determined by facts about reasons.²⁰

But this is not the response I'm inclined towards. If you reject the Connection Principles, then you think that oughts can float-free from reasons in surprising ways. You're committed to saying that Suzy ought to play the game, even though there's no good reason for her to do so, and that Suzy should push one of the buttons on the panel even though there's more reason for her to take the cash. This kind of decoupling of oughts from reasons is not only, I think, philosophically unattractive – it also appears to be resisted by ordinary speakers. See, for example, the rather strange:

(10a) # You ought to visit Europe, but there's no good reason for you to.

(10b) # You ought to visit Europe, but the reasons for you to go to Asia are stronger.

I think we should want to hang onto the Connection Principles unless we're forced to give them up.

The alternative way of going is to endorse a non-monotonic semantics for 'ought' – a semantics that does not license an inference from (i) to (ii). In a second, I'm going to turn to sketching one. First, I highlight three of its distinctive features.

²⁰ I'm thinking in particular of the 'austere' theory of reasons in Horty (2012). It's a corollary of Horty's theory that sometimes you ought to do something even though there's no reason for you to do it (2012, p.45).

Firstly, and most importantly, I'm going to build certain connections between oughts and reasons into the semantics itself. The Connection Principles are, in effect, going to fall out of the semantics as corollaries.

Secondly, while the semantics is non-monotonic, and so will make the following sentence true (where the 'not' scopes over the ought-claim),

(11a) Suzy ought to push Button 3, but it's not the case that she ought to play the game.

the semantics renders the following false (where the ought-claim scopes over the 'not'):

(11b) Suzy ought to push Button 3, but she ought not play the game.

I'm inclined to think this is the right result. We should want to hold onto the idea that Suzy can do all the things she ought to do. (11b) cannot be true, because it's not possible for Suzy to both push Button 3 and not play the game. More generally, the semantics is going to satisfy *Joint Satisfiability*:

Joint Satisfiability: If S ought to Φ and S ought to Ψ , it's possible for S to [Φ and Ψ].

I highlight this feature of the semantics because *Procrastinate*-style cases like *Suzy's Game* are sometimes used to motivate actualist analyses of 'ought', and actualist analyses of 'ought' are typically not compatible with Joint Satisfiability.²¹ But there are good reasons to want to preserve the principle.²² The semantics I present below does so. (See Appendix A.2 for a proof.)

Thirdly, along with presenting a semantics for the weak modals ('ought', 'should'), I'm also going to present a semantics for the strong modals ('have to', 'need to', 'must'). And I'm going to do so in a perhaps

²¹ Roughly speaking, according to actualist accounts of 'ought' (see e.g. Jackson & Pargetter 1986), S ought to Φ iff things would be better if S Φ -d than they would be if S didn't Φ . Applied to *Suzy's Game* this yields the result that she ought to push Button 3, but she ought not play.

²² For a case in favour of Joint Satisfiability, see Kiesewetter (2018a).

surprising way: while the account makes the weak modals non-monotonic, the strong modals will continue to exhibit a kind of monotonicity.²³

This final feature of the semantics deserves special comment. It's already well-established that there's a difference in meaning between 'ought' and 'have to'.²⁴ We all understand the rules governing seatbelt usage on commercial flights: when the seatbelt sign is lit-up, you have to keep your seatbelt on (and hence you ought to); when the seatbelt sign isn't lit up, you don't *have to* keep your seatbelt on but you still should. However, while it's one thing to say that 'ought' and 'have to' have different meanings, it's quite another to say they have different logics. Why think so?

I have two motivations. Firstly, the cases that motivate treating 'ought' non-monotonically do not seem to motivate treating 'have to' non-monotonically – or at least, I think one's judgements with respect to the latter are much less clear-cut. Notice to begin with, that *Suzy's Game*, as written, offers no support for abandoning the monotonicity of 'have to' or 'must'. Consider:

(12a) Suzy has to / must push Button 3.

(12b) Suzy has to / must play the game.

For sure, (12b) is false in the case described. But so is (12a). It would be *best* if Suzy pushed Button 3. That's what there's most reason for her to do. But she doesn't have to.

One might worry that this is just an artefact of the case as described, and that raising the moral stakes will shift our judgements. For example, following a suggestion from an anonymous referee, we might suppose that Suzy promised her friend she'd repay a debt of £100, and that the only way for her to repay that debt

²³ I say the strong modals will exhibit a *kind* of monotonicity, because the semantics doesn't make them fully monotonic, just 'Strawson' monotonic. See §4.3.

²⁴ See, among others, von Fintel & Iatridou (2008, 2023).

and keep her promise is to push Button 3. For the sake of argument, let's imagine that this twist to the case is sufficient to make (12a) true. What should we think about (12b)?

I take it that judgements here are fragile, but here's what I think. If (12a) is true, (12b) cannot be false. For if Suzy doesn't have to play the game, then it must be permissible for Suzy to take the cash.²⁵ But if it's permissible for Suzy to take the cash, then it can't be true that she has to push Button 3 – after all, there's another permissible option open to her. So there's no monotonicity violation: when we raise the stakes so (12a) is true, we must drop the claim that (12b) is false.

So I think there's some good intuitive support for continuing to treat 'have to' monotonically. My second motivation for doing so is linguistic: the hypothesis that 'have to' is monotonic nicely explains a couple of pieces of linguistic data. See, for example, abominable conjunctions like the following:

- (13) # Charlie doesn't have to wear a tie or a scarf, but he has to wear a tie. (Von Stechow, 2012, p.13)

The hypothesis that 'have to' is upwards monotonic gives an elegant explanation for why (13) is unacceptable. For if 'have to' is monotonic, the two conjuncts contradict each other.

Here's another piece of data. One trick used by linguists to figure out whether an environment is upwards monotonic is to check whether its negation is *downwards* monotonic. And one way of figuring out whether an environment is downwards monotonic is to check whether it licenses Negative Polarity Items (NPIs) – expressions like *ever*, *at all*, *any*, *lift a finger*, *budge an inch*. And, indeed, NPIs can appear felicitously under 'don't have to':

- (14a) I would like it if you relaxed on the couch while I tidy up: you don't have to lift a finger.

²⁵ I'm assuming *S may Φ* is true iff *S doesn't have to not- Φ* is true.

- (14b) The boss will give in to your demands if you are stubborn: you don't have to budge an inch.

It's significant that the semantics I offer below captures the abominable conjunction and NPI data. For in recent literature, some authors²⁶ have used this data as part of a case not just for the monotonicity of 'have to', but also for the monotonicity of 'ought'. (This is despite the fact that the data is not cleanly replicable with the weak modals, as these authors acknowledge.²⁷) The background assumption, presumably, is that if 'have to' is monotonic, 'ought' will be too. The semantics I offer below demonstrates that this background assumption can in principle be rejected. We can treat 'have to' monotonically, accommodate the above data, preserve the intuitive connections between 'have to' and 'ought' (in particular, their asymmetric entailments), yet still give 'ought' a non-monotonic semantics. But no more delays – let's get to the account.

§4 Sketching a reasonable semantics

4.1 The basics

Let's start by granting ourselves a big simplifying assumption: for any agent S and option of theirs Φ , there's always some answer to the question *how much reason is there for S to Φ* ? The most convenient way of representing this formally is via a function \mathbf{R} that maps pairs of agents and options $\langle S, \Phi \rangle$ to real numbers that represent how much reason S has to take that option. For short, I call $\mathbf{R}(\langle S, \Phi \rangle)$ the *reasonableness* of

²⁶ I'm thinking especially of von Stechow (2012) and Muñoz and Spencer (2020).

²⁷ The tests for monotonicity – both the abominable conjunction test and the NPI test – rely on embedding the relevant linguistic environment under negation. And while 'have to' can easily be negated (as in, 'don't have to'), 'ought' and the other weak necessity modals (e.g. 'should') cannot. See Iatridou & Zeijlstra (2013). Consider "You ought not dance". There is no interpretation of this sentence on which the negation takes wide scope over the modal (i.e. as *NOT ought dance*). The same thing appears to hold for expressions that lexicalise negation: the sentence 'I doubt you ought to dance' is more naturally read as *I believe you ought not dance* than *I believe it's not the case that you ought to dance*. Now, granted, in English you can apparently force the negation to take wide scope with 'it's not the case that...', 'it's not true that...', 'I doubt it's true that...', etc. But it's not obvious that these kinds of sentences will be probative in the present context. And even if they are probative, the results are inconclusive. "Suzy ought to push Button 3, but it's not true that she ought to push some button or other between 1 and 100" sounds much less bad to me than the abominable 'have to' conjunctions. It's also unclear to me whether NPIs are felicitous under "it's not the case that you ought to". (See, e.g., the rather odd "It's not the case that you ought to lift a finger.")

S's Φ ing. (In what follows I normally suppress the argument place for the agent, and speak as though \mathbf{R} is a function from actions to numbers, rather than pairs of actions *and agents* to numbers – it should always be kept in mind that, strictly speaking, I mean the latter).

The claim that reasonableness can be modelled with anything as precise as real numbers is inessential to the semantics, and can be jettisoned without anything of consequence being lost. Nonetheless, the claim betrays something quite strong I'm assuming in the background. I'm assuming that an agent's options can be *totally ordered* by the amount of reason there is to do them: that is, for any two options Φ and Ψ , there's either more reason to Φ than Ψ , more reason to Ψ than Φ , or equally as much reason to Φ as there is to Ψ . Personally, I'm inclined to think this is what we *should* say. Just look at the ordinary inferences involving the mass noun 'reason' we're naturally inclined to make (c.f. the evidence in favour of comparability theses marshalled in Dorr et al. 2022):

There's no more reason to visit France than there is to visit Spain. *So*: there's just as much reason to visit Spain as there is to visit France.

There's not as much reason to visit Spain as there is to visit Germany. *So*: there's more reason to visit Germany than there is to visit Spain.

But there is of course a long history of hostility to this kind of comparability thesis in the normative domain²⁸, and it would be nice if the semantics presented here did not rely on something so strong. Thankfully, I'm cautiously optimistic that the semantics can be tweaked to allow for \mathbf{R} merely partially ordering an agent's options. (See Appendix A4.) For now, though, I'll write assuming that the ordering provided by \mathbf{R} is total.

There is a good case to be made that the normative sense of 'reason' is context sensitive. For example, it seems I can say "there is most reason for Suzy to push Button 3" and communicate (truly) that given all the

²⁸ See, among many others, Chang (2002).

facts, pushing Button 3 would be best, or (falsely) that given the information she has available to her, pushing Button 3 would be best. For now, we can make room for this kind of context-sensitivity by positing many **R**-functions – at least as many as there are normative flavours of the English word ‘reason’. In general, we can say that \mathbf{R}_c corresponds to whichever sense of (mass noun) ‘reason’ is operative in the context c . Far more needs to be said, but the analysis I give here should be compatible with a wide range of approaches to the context sensitivity of reason talk.

For $\mathbf{R}(\langle S, \Phi \rangle)$ to be well-defined, Φ needs to be an option for S . It shouldn’t matter too much which theory of options you endorse, but what is important is that an agent’s options can be more or less fine-grained. One of Suzy’s options is *push Button 3*, and another option is *play the game*. Given the non-monotonicity of ‘reason’, sometimes a specific action will be more reasonable than a non-specific action it entails. For example:

$$\mathbf{R}(\langle \text{Suzy}, \text{push Button 3} \rangle) > \mathbf{R}(\langle \text{Suzy}, \text{play the game} \rangle)$$

Now, given an agent and their options, we can order the actions open to them by their **R**-value. Plausibly, an incomplete slice of the **R**-values in Suzy’s case is as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 3}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{play the game}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 1}) \dots$$

One final piece to put in place. I follow Cariani (2011) and Snedegar (2012) in assuming that context determines some baseline value b_c . I call actions whose **R**-value exceeds b_c ‘minimally reasonable’. For now it will do no harm to assume the baseline in the above model goes just below *play the game*:

$$\mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 3}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{play the game}) > b_c > \mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 1}) \dots$$

Onto the semantics. Let’s start with the strong modal, ‘have to’. Intuitively, *S has to Φ* is true iff every minimally reasonable option requires Φ ing. In our framework:

Approximate meaning of ‘have to’:

$$[[S \text{ has to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

i.e. *S has to Φ* is true in context *c* iff all minimally reasonable actions (according to the standards of minimal reasonableness in *c*) are ways of Φ ing.

What about ‘ought’? The asymmetrical entailments between the strong and weak modals suggest that while ‘have to’ tracks what needs to be done in order to be good enough, ‘ought’ tracks what’s *best*.²⁹ That might suggest that ‘S ought to Φ ’ is true just when Φ ing has the highest **R**-value:

Ought as best (incorrect semantics):

$$[[S \text{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi [\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi)]$$

But this cannot be quite right. We can imagine it’s best for Suzy to push Button 3 using her right arm – perhaps her left arm is slightly sore. If so, when fleshed out a little more, our (still incomplete) model should look something like this:

$$\mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 3 with right arm}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 3}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\text{play the game}) > b_c > \mathbf{R}(\text{push Button 1}) \dots$$

Now *push Button 3* isn’t the highest ranked option. Nonetheless, it’s still true that this is what she ought to do.

²⁹ An anonymous referee suggests that, to capture this insight, we could posit two baselines – a less demanding one and a more demanding one – and say that *S ought to Φ* is true iff every action more reasonable than the more demanding baseline entails Φ . Such an account would be elegant, and secures much of what we wanted. But it doesn’t secure everything, for notice it’ll make ‘ought’ upwards monotonic. Insofar as you’re persuaded by my arguments in §2, this is not the way we should go.

We can rescue the insight behind the ‘ought as best’ suggestion by weakening it slightly: ‘ought Φ ’ doesn’t say Φ ing beats *all* other actions, only that it beats every action *except, perhaps, those which are themselves ways of Φ ing*. This gloss is truth-conditionally equivalent to the claim that any action which is more reasonable than Φ entails Φ ing:

Approximate meaning of ‘ought’:

$$[[S \text{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi [(R_c(\Psi) \geq R_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

i.e. S ought to Φ is true in context c iff any action that’s at least reasonable as Φ (according to the standards of reasonableness in c) is itself just a way of Φ ing. Contraposing: for every action Ψ that isn’t a way of Φ ing, there is strictly more reason for S to Φ than Ψ .

With this entry, we secure a rather nice result: the meanings of the strong modal ‘have to’ and the weak modal ‘ought to’ are very similar indeed. S has to Φ says that any action more reasonable than the *baseline* is a way of Φ ing. S ought to Φ says that any action more reasonable than Φ is a way of Φ ing. An equivalent way of thinking about the semantics for ‘ought’, then, is that ‘ought Φ ’ means the same thing as ‘have to Φ ’, except when we make an ought-claim the baseline is moved upwards from its default value to a stricter standard.

4.2 Two tweaks to the semantics

There are two tweaks to make to the semantics before I tie everything together.

First tweak. As things stand, ‘ S has to Φ ’ is true only if *every* option more reasonable than the baseline entails Φ ing, and ‘ S ought to Φ ’ is true only if *every* option more reasonable than Φ entails Φ ing. This turns out to be too strong.

To see why, let's temporarily tweak *Suzy's Game*, and suppose that Suzy is able to both take the cash and play the game. On this variant of the case, all of the following should come out true:

- (i) Suzy ought to push Button 3 and take the cash.
- (ii) Suzy ought to push Button 3.
- (iii) Suzy ought to take the cash.

But this result is inconsistent with the semantics, as written. For the relevant slice of R-values is presumably going to look like this:

$$\mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 3 and take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 3}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{take the cash}) > \dots$$

Given this ordering, and the semantics for 'ought' in the previous section, (i) and (ii) will come out true, but (iii) will come out false. For not every action more reasonable than *take the cash* is a way of taking the cash. The action *push Button 3* can be performed in good ways (while taking the cash) and bad ways (while leaving the cash on the table).

Here's my suggested fix. To evaluate whether an agent ought to Φ , we don't check whether *all* actions more reasonable than Φ are ways of Φ ing. Instead, we should restrict the quantifiers in our semantics to a set A , whose members are all and only the agent's maximally-specific options:

$$\begin{aligned} [[S \textit{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE} & \text{ iff } \quad \forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \textit{ entails } \Phi] \\ [[S \textit{ has to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE} & \text{ iff } \quad \forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \textit{ entails } \Phi] \end{aligned}$$

Now "Suzy ought to take the cash" is going to come out true, in the above context. Every maximally specific action more reasonable than taking the cash is, itself, just a way of taking the cash. The action *push Button 3* isn't maximally specific (it can be performed in better or worse ways), so it's not in A , and so it cannot falsify the ought-claim.

What is it for an action to be maximally specific? Officially, I’m agnostic. Perhaps standards of specificity vary between contexts, and so while an action like *push Button 3* doesn’t count as maximally specific in the above context, it would qualify as maximally specific in other contexts. Alternatively, the semantics could be supplemented with some substantive theory of maximal specificity. (For example, perhaps an action is in A just in case it’s a member of the maximally fine-grained partition of actions that the agent has direct control over.) Either way, we’ll need to impose some constraints on \mathbf{R} to make sure it’s well-behaved with respect to A . I discuss one (weak) constraint we might choose to impose in Appendix A.1.

That’s the first tweak to the semantics. Onto the second tweak. As things stand, ‘S has to Φ ’ and ‘S ought to Φ ’ can be true even when the reasonableness of Φ is arbitrarily low. This is not only intuitively implausible, but it also ends up breaking the entailment from ‘have to’ to ‘ought’.³⁰ Here is my suggested fix: for ‘S has to Φ ’ or ‘S ought to Φ ’ to be true, Φ ing must be minimally reasonable. The most straightforward way of cashing this out formally is to impose the following presupposition:

S has to Φ (and *S ought to Φ*) is well-defined in c only if either $\mathbf{R}(\Phi) > b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}(\sim\Phi) > b_c$.³¹

If neither Φ nor $\sim\Phi$ appear among the options above the baseline, then neither ‘ought Φ ’ nor ‘has to Φ ’ can be true.

This presupposition allows the semantics to capture the entailment from ‘have to’ to ‘ought’ as well as some connection principles between ‘have to’ and reason claims. See Appendix A.1. for more details.

³⁰ Suppose our model was

$\mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 3}) > b_c > \mathbf{R}(\textit{take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{play the game}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 1}) \dots$

Suppose too that every action except *play the game* is maximally specific. Without tweaking the semantics, *Suzy has to play the game* would come out true, but *Suzy ought to play the game* would come out false.

³¹ The second disjunct is needed to accommodate cases where deontic modals are negated (we don’t want *you don’t have to commit mass murder* to presuppose that *commit mass murder* is minimally reasonable).

This gives us our final entries for the two modals:

A reasonable meaning for ‘have to’

$$[[S \text{ has to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

presupposition: either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$

In other words: *S has to* Φ is well-defined only if either Φ ing or not- Φ ing is minimally reasonable, and (assuming it’s well-defined) it’s true iff all specific, minimally reasonable actions entail Φ ing.³²

A reasonable meaning for ‘ought to’

$$[[S \text{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

presupposition: either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$

In other words: *S ought to* Φ is well-defined only if either Φ ing or not- Φ ing is minimally reasonable, and (assuming it’s well-defined) it’s true iff any specific action that’s at least as reasonable as Φ is just, itself, a way of Φ ing.

4.3 The payoff

The semantics has only been roughly sketched, but it already gets us much of what we wanted.

Let’s start with ‘have to’. In the previous section, I pointed to data which suggests ‘have to’ obeys a kind of monotonicity. Firstly, conjunctions like the following always seem unassertable:

³² What about permissibility? The most straightforward thing to do here is treat permission as the dual of obligation and say that *S may* Φ is true iff S doesn’t have to not- Φ (i.e. iff $\exists \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \ \& \ \Psi \text{ doesn't entail not-}\Phi]$). Plausibly, for any non-specific action Φ , every maximally specific action is either a way of Φ -ing or it’s a way of not- Φ ing. If so, then our definition collapses into the claim that *S may* Φ is true iff there’s a maximally specific way of Φ ing that appears above the baseline.

- (13) # Charlie doesn't have to wear a tie or a scarf, but he has to wear a tie. (Von Fintel, 2012, p.13)

Secondly, 'don't have to' licenses NPIs. For example:

- (14a) I would like it if you relaxed on the couch while I tidy up: you don't have to lift a finger.

The reasonable semantics explains both pieces of data. With respect to the abominable conjunction, notice that if the second conjunct of (13) is true, then all the specific actions above b_c entail wearing a tie. But that means all the specific actions above b_c entail wearing a tie or a scarf. So "you have to wear a tie or a scarf" must be true too, which contradicts the first conjunct. So (13) can never be true – hence its unassertability.

A similar story goes for the NPI data. According to our semantics, *have to* is 'Strawson' monotonic: whenever Φ ing entails Ψ ing, if c is a context in which both *S has to Φ* and *S has to Ψ* are well-defined, then if *S has to Φ* is true in c , so is *S has to Ψ* . There's good evidence for the claim that Strawson monotonic environments license NPIs when negated.³³

Despite the (Strawson) monotonicity of 'have to', 'ought' is non-monotonic. Take a look at this model of Suzy's situation again (and assume, for simplicity, that all the actions except *play the game* are maximally specific):

$\mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 3}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{take the cash}) > \mathbf{R}(\textit{play the game}) > b_c > \mathbf{R}(\textit{push Button 1}) \dots$

³³ For more on Strawson monotonicity and the licensing of NPIs, see von Fintel (1999). I also note, in passing, that the idea that 'have to' isn't fully monotonic, but instead 'Strawson' monotonic, may help explain why 'Suzy has to play the game' can sound objectionable even in a context where the only minimally decent option open to Suzy is one that involves Button 3. It's not that this sentence is *false* in such a context. (It can never be the case that Φ ing entails Ψ ing, an agent has to Φ but they don't have to Ψ .) What's going wrong, perhaps, is that the sentence has an unsatisfied presupposition (namely, that *playing the game* falls above the baseline).

Recall, *ought* Φ is true iff any specific action that's more reasonable than Φ is itself just a way of Φ ing. Given our semantics, the above model makes (i) true but (ii) false.

- (i) Suzy ought to push Button 3.
- (ii) Suzy ought to play the game.

(i) is true because every specific action more reasonable than *push Button 3* is itself a way of pushing Button 3 (in fact, on the above simplified model, there is no action more reasonable than *push Button 3*). (ii) is false because there's a specific action (namely, *take the cash*) which is more reasonable than *play the game* but which isn't a way of playing the game.

Generally, we will get counterexamples to the monotonicity of 'ought' whenever Φ ing entails Ψ ing, the agent ought to Φ , but there is a sufficiently big gap between the amount of reason the agent has to Φ and the amount of reason they have to Ψ . The gap between the reasonableness of Φ ing and Ψ ing is 'big enough' to get monotonicity failure when there is a specific action which *isn't* a way of Ψ ing that appears between the two.³⁴

The fact that our semantics for 'ought' is non-monotonic means it's compatible with the Connection Principles. But in fact we end up with something more interesting than this: by constructing our semantics in terms of reason-to-act, the Connection Principles simply drop out of the meanings we've assigned to 'have to' and 'ought'. (See Appendix A.3).

³⁴ Notice that the semantics allows for *S ought to* Φ to be true even when there's a relevant/salient way of Φ ing that falls below the baseline. This is in contrast with the non-monotonic analysis given in Cariani (2011). I think the semantics gets things right on this point. For example, we should want the claim "Suzy ought not push Button 17" to be true. But not every relevant way of *not pushing Button 17* falls above the baseline. (Notice that you can *not push Button 17* by pushing Button 18.) On the above semantics, the relevant ought claim comes out true, because, presumably, there's more reason not to push Button 17 than there is to push it (in any maximally specific way). See Blumberg & Hawthorne 2021, §3.4 for a version of this kind of criticism levelled at Cariani.

§5 Conclusion

The idea that ought-facts and reason-facts are connected is both highly intuitive and philosophically fruitful. But the implications of this idea for natural language semantics have, I think, been overlooked. This paper argued for one such implication: if the Connection Principles hold, then ‘ought’ is not monotonic, and hence the standard semantics for deontic modals must be rejected. The second half of the paper sketched the direction that I think we should go in next. I presented a semantics which took the Connection Principles seriously by building them into the meanings of deontic modals.

Our discussion leaves some important philosophical and semantic questions still to be answered. I close by highlighting two.

Firstly, notice that while the semantics above captures connections between ought and the mass noun ‘reason’ (the sense of ‘reason’ that appears in “there’s lots of reason to Φ ”), there are arguably connections between ought and the *count* sense of ‘reason’ (the sense of ‘reason’ that appears in “there are three reasons to Φ ”) that we might want to capture too. Perhaps, for example:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| (Good Reason _{COUNT}) | If S ought to Φ , there is <i>a</i> good reason to Φ . |
| (Decisive Reason _{COUNT}) | S ought to Φ iff there’s <i>a</i> decisive reason to Φ . |

If we want to have these kinds of connections drop out as semantic entailments then we need to say more about how the count and mass senses of ‘reason’ are related.³⁵ I leave the question of which further kinds of connections we want, and whether the reasonable semantics can capture them, for another day.

One of the most important semantic issues that remains, I take it, is the question of what we should say about non-deontic flavours of ‘ought’ and ‘have to’. One of the attractions of the Kratzerian picture is that

³⁵ See Fogal (2016), Fogal & Risberg (2023) for an analysis of reasons in terms of reason. See Watkins (2025) for an analysis of reason in terms of reasons. (On the latter analysis, “there is reason” will entail “there is a reason”.)

it can handle oughts of all different flavours without positing an ambiguity. What should a defender of the ‘reasonable’ semantics say about non-deontic oughts?

As it happens, I am optimistic that something along the lines of the above semantics could be extended (with a bit of tweaking) to at least *some* other domains. For notice that there appear to be connections between ‘ought’ and ‘reason’ even outside the domain of ethics. Take epistemic flavours of ‘ought’:

(15a) (According to my evidence...) Bob ought to be in his office.

An assertion of (15a) would seem to commit a speaker to the following:

(15b) There’s some reason to believe that Bob is in his office.

(15c) There’s more reason to believe that Bob is in his office than that he is at home.

But it’s much more difficult to know what to say about so-called ‘circumstantial’ flavours. See, for example:

(16a) Rhododendrons should grow here. (The soil has enough moisture.)

On the face of it, (16a) does not seem to entail

(16b) ? There’s more reason for Rhododendrons to grow here than there is for them not to.

So perhaps, in the end, a commitment to the reasonable semantics will involve a commitment to there being multiple senses of ‘ought’. I’m not going to decide the issue here, nor assess what the costs would be of opting for some kind of ambiguity theory.³⁶ Either way, the idea that a substantial part of our modal thought and talk is shot through with connections to reasons is exciting and worth taking seriously.

³⁶ For a case in favour of modal polysemy, see Vetter & Viebahn (2016).

Appendix

A.1 ‘Have to’ entails ‘ought to’

Recall that in §4.2 I restricted the quantifiers in ‘have to’ and ‘ought’ to a set of maximally specific actions A . In order to capture the entailment between ‘have to’ and ‘ought’, we need to begin to impose some constraints on \mathbf{R} . We can get quite far just by saying the following:

Reason Requires a Reasonable Way (RRRW):

$$\forall \Psi [\exists \Psi_w \in A (\Psi_w \text{ entails } \Psi \text{ and } \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi_w) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi))]$$

i.e. For all actions Ψ , there exists a specific way of Ψ -ing, Ψ_w , such that Ψ_w is at least as reasonable as Ψ .

In effect, RRRW amounts to this plausible claim: it’s never the case that Ψ -ing is strictly more reasonable than every specific way of Ψ -ing. e.g. You can never have more reason to push *some button or other* than you do to push any particular button.³⁷

³⁷ Suppose we didn’t have this constraint. Then there’s nothing to rule out a model that looks like this (where Φ_w is a specific way of Φ -ing, and $\Psi_1, \Psi_2 \dots$ are specific ways of not Φ -ing):

$$\mathbf{R}(\Phi_w) > \mathbf{R}(\text{not-}\Phi) > \mathbf{R}(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}(\Psi_1) > \mathbf{R}(\Psi_2) \dots$$

On this model, it’ll end up being true that you ought to Φ , as all the specific actions more reasonable than Φ entail Φ -ing. But it’s also true that you have more reason to not- Φ than Φ . That’s a violation of the Connection Principles.

RRRW is a very weak constraint. In the long run, I suspect we'll want to replace it with something stronger.³⁸ But RRRW is sufficient by itself to ensure that if 'S has to Φ ' is true in a context c , so is 'S ought to Φ '. Here's a reminder of the two entries:

$$[[S \text{ has to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \quad \forall \Psi \in A \ [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

presupposition: either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$

$$[[S \text{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \quad \forall \Psi \in A \ [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

presupposition: either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$

Here's the proof:

- (1) Suppose *S has to Φ* is true in c .
- (2) either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$ [1, presupp. of 'have to' satisfied]
- (3) $\forall \Psi \in A \ [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$ [1, truth conditions for 'have to']
- (4) *Assumption: $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$*
- (5) $\exists \Psi \in A \ [\Psi \text{ entails not-}\Phi \ \& \ \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c]$ [4, RRRW]
- Contradiction!* [3, 5]
- (6) $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ [2, 4, disjunctive syllogism]
- (7) $\forall \Psi \in A \ [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$ [3, 6]

³⁸ For example, RRRW alone won't get us Weakening:

Weakening: *Ought*(Φ) & *Ought*(Ψ) entails *Ought*(Φ or Ψ)

The following is a countermodel to Weakening that respects RRRW (where the conjunctions Φ & Ψ , $\sim\Phi$ & $\sim\Psi$, Φ & $\sim\Psi$, and $\sim\Phi$ and Ψ are the only maximally specific options):

$$\mathbf{R}(\Phi \ \& \ \Psi) > \mathbf{R}(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}(\Psi) > \mathbf{R}(\sim\Phi \ \& \ \sim\Psi) > \mathbf{R}(\Phi \ \text{or} \ \Psi) > b_c > \mathbf{R}(\Phi \ \& \ \sim\Psi) > \mathbf{R}(\sim\Phi \ \& \ \Psi)$$

(Thanks to Kyle Blumberg for pointing this out.) On this model, *ought Φ* is true, *ought Ψ* is true but *ought (Φ or Ψ)* is false. The funny thing about this model – the thing driving the Weakening failure – is that somehow the agent has less reason to Φ or Ψ than they have reason to Φ or reason to Ψ . If we want to hang onto Weakening, ultimately we'll want a constraint that prevents the reasonableness of a disjunctive action from dropping lower than the reasonableness of both disjuncts. I leave the project of motivating and developing these constraints on \mathbf{R} for another time.

(8) S ought to Φ is true in c [2, 7, truth conditions for ‘ought’]

A.2 ‘Ought’ satisfies Joint Satisfiability

Recall:

Joint Satisfiability: If S ought to Φ_1 and S ought to Φ_2 , it’s possible for S to [Φ_1 and Φ_2]

Suppose, for reductio, that:

- (1) S ought to Φ_1 is true in c
- (2) S ought to Φ_2 is true in c
- (3) Φ_1 entails *not*- Φ_2

We can derive a contradiction:

- (4) Suppose $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_1) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_2)$
- (5) $\exists \Psi \in A$ (Ψ entails Φ_1 & $\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_2)$) [4, RRW]
- (6) $\exists \Psi \in A$ (Ψ entails *not*- Φ_2 & $\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_2)$) [5, 3]
- (7) $\forall \Psi \in A$ [$(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_2)) \rightarrow \Psi$ entails Φ_2] [2, def. of ‘ought’]
- Contradiction!* [6, 7]

We can derive a contradiction by similar reasoning if we assume instead that $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_2) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi_1)$.

A.3 The reasonable semantics captures the Connection Principles

Here, I show that our reasonable semantics captures analogues of the Connection Principles:

$\forall \Psi \in \text{alt}(\Phi), \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi)$	iff
$\forall \Psi [(\Psi \in A \text{ and } \Psi \text{ doesn't entail } \Phi) \rightarrow \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi)]$	iff
$\forall \Psi \in A [\Psi \text{ doesn't entail } \Phi \rightarrow \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi)]$	iff
$\forall \Psi \in A [\sim(\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi)) \rightarrow \sim(\Psi \text{ doesn't entail } \Phi)]$	iff
$\forall \Psi \in A [\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$	iff
S ought to Φ	

A nice bonus of the fact that ‘have to’ is not fully monotonic (but merely Strawson-monotonic) is that we get some Connection Principles between ‘have to’ and ‘reason’. For example:

(More Reason*)	If <i>S has to Φ</i> is true, then there is more reason for S to Φ than there is reason for S to not- Φ .
(Most Reason*)	If <i>S has to Φ</i> is true, then there is most reason for S to Φ .

These follow from the fact that ‘S has to Φ ’ entails ‘S ought to Φ ’, and that ‘S ought to Φ ’ entails both ‘there is more reason to Φ than not- Φ ’ and ‘there is most reason to Φ ’. What we won’t get is the other direction of ‘Most Reason*’:

If S has most reason to Φ , then S has to Φ . (False)

But this seems like exactly the right result. There’s most reason for me to keep my seatbelt on at all times on a flight. I still don’t have to.

A.4 Extending the semantics to partial orderings

As promised, here I sketch one possible direction forward if we wish to drop the assumption that \mathbf{R} totally orders one’s options. Thanks go to an anonymous referee here, whose comments led me to think more seriously about this.

Take a classic ‘small improvement’ case (c.f. Chang 2002). Suppose you can choose between:

X : a holiday in France,

Y : a holiday in Spain, or

$Y+$: a holiday in Spain plus \$10.

Suppose too (for the sake of argument) that we cannot totally order these options by the amount of reason there is to take them. There are incomparabilities:

$$\mathbf{R}(Y+) > \mathbf{R}(Y)$$

$$\mathbf{R}(Y) \sim \mathbf{R}(X)$$

$$\mathbf{R}(Y+) \sim \mathbf{R}(X)$$

If this is the right way of describing the case, then the semantics provided above returns the result that you *both* ought to X and ought to $Y+$.³⁹ In other words, you’re facing a deontic dilemma. This would appear to be the wrong result.

The obvious corrective move to be made is to say that for *ought* Φ to be true it’s required not only that all (maximally specific) actions at-least-as-reasonable-as Φ entail Φ ing, but in addition that all (maximally specific) *incomparable* actions entail Φ ing. This yields the following entry (writing ‘ $x \succeq y$ ’ to mean x is either (i) strictly greater than y , or (ii) equal to y , or (iii) incomparable to y):

$$[[S \text{ ought to } \Phi]]^c = \text{TRUE iff } \forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$$

presupposition: either $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$ or $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \geq b_c$

³⁹ Notice that every maximally specific action at-least-as-reasonable-as X entails X . *Mutatis mutandis* for $Y+$.

Now in the above case both *you ought to X* and *you ought to Y+* will come out false. Assuming too that there's strictly more reason to *X or Y+* than there is to *Y*, we get the (correct) result that you ought either to *X* or to *Y+*.

The central results of this paper (the entailment from *have to* to *ought*, the Connection Principles) go through on this tweaked semantics provided we make the following assumptions:

Assumption I: $\forall \Psi (\Psi \geq b_c \text{ or } b_c \geq \Psi)$,

i.e. every option is comparable to the baseline

Assumption II: If $X \geq Y$ and $Y \gtrsim Z$, then $X \gtrsim Z$

i.e. if *X* is at least as good as *Y*, and *Y* is not strictly worse than *Z*, then *X* is not strictly worse than *Z*.

I won't reproduce all the proofs here, as they are mostly unchanged. Instead, I highlight their key differences. The crucial step in the proof that *have to* entails *ought* is the following:

(i) $\forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \geq b_c) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$ and

(ii) $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq b_c$

Therefore: $\forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \gtrsim \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi]$

To see why this is valid, suppose for *reductio* that there exists some maximally specific action α which doesn't entail Φ and is such that $\mathbf{R}_c(\alpha) \sim \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)$. Given Assumption I, either $\alpha \geq b_c$ or $b_c \geq \alpha$. Given (i), we can deduce that $b_c \geq \alpha$. Given (ii) and the transitivity of \geq , it follows that $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \geq \alpha$. But this contradicts our assumption that $\mathbf{R}_c(\alpha) \sim \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)$.

The proof that *Ought* entails *More Reason* uses Assumption II.

- (1) Suppose *S ought to Φ* is true in *c*.
- (2) $\forall \Psi \in A [(\mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) \rightarrow \Psi \text{ entails } \Phi)]$ [1, truth conditions for ‘ought’]
- (3) *Assumption: $\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)$*
- (4) $\exists \Psi \in A [\Psi \text{ entails not-}\Phi \ \& \ \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi)]$ [3, RRRW]
- (5) $\exists \Psi \in A [\Psi \text{ entails not-}\Phi \ \& \ \mathbf{R}_c(\Psi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)]$ [3, 4, Assumption II]
- Contradiction!* [2, 5]
- (6) $\sim[\mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi) \succeq \mathbf{R}_c(\Phi)]$ [*Reductio*]
- (7) $\mathbf{R}_c(\Phi) > \mathbf{R}_c(\text{not-}\Phi)$ [6]

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